

Bukidnon-Magahat Learners' Plight : Factors Affecting Learning Academic Performance

Ma. Nova Joy R. Alcueres, MAEd

Public School Teacher, DepEd-Bayawan City Division, Bayawan City, Negros Oriental, Philippines

Abstract

This study aimed to identify the factors that influences indigenous learners academic performance. A population of 139 indigenous learners from grades 4-6 were the research respondents in the public schools in the Division of Bayawan City. This research utilized the Descriptive-Correlational method and statistical tools were used to answer the specific problems. Results revealed that indigenous learners showed a high extent on their individual, instructional, and socio-cultural perceived factors. Moreover, the data indicated that the academic performance of the respondents on the core subjects such as English, Science, and Mathematics is "Fairly Satisfactory" on the first quarter and satisfactory level during the second quarter. Lastly, there is strong relationship between the individual factors like study habits, academic self-concept, and confidence in academic life on their academic performance. While they are on moderate relationship in their interest. A very weak relationship on instructional factors, and moderate extent on parental support.

Keywords: *Indigenous learners, individual factors, instructional factors, socio-cultural factors, academic performance*

Introduction

Indigenous peoples' right to education is enshrined in Philippine Constitution wherein it states that "The Philippine government shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all"(Art.XIV, Sec.1). This is then supported with the enactment of Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act (IPRA), United Nation Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) and then later, realized through the adaptation of Indigenous Peoples' Education (IPed) Policy and Framework (DepEd Order no.32, series of 2015) to make learner-centered, contextualized, and culture-sensitive indigenous learners (Luistro, 2011).

Despite the existence of national legislations, Bradley, Draca, Green and Leeves, (2007) revealed that indigenous minority groups in Australia, Canada, New Zealand, United States and Philippines are severely disadvantage according to a range of socio-economic indicators that hinders of having a culturally relevant quality education.

The study of De Bortoli and Thomson (2009) provided that there are still large gaps in the socio-economic background of indigenous learners. Less educational resources means that many indigenous children start school at disadvantage. They are more likely to miss school on regular basis especially during harvest season. Lower achievement and discontinuity of schooling can lead to lower levels of academic performance/achievement.

In Philippine educational context, indigenous students such as "Igorots" in Benguet were discriminated and bullied as "Uplanders/Highlanders" with dark skin, thick lips and kinky hair when mainstreamed to a dominant population. This implies that "Igorots" need to adjust their traditional way of learning to mainstream approaches, making them feel inferior with their

identity. This manifested that “Igorots” have less confidence and most likely not to attend school (Adonis and Couch, 2017).

Nonetheless, it was clearly stated that indigenous learners were of disadvantage in school. The situation was observed by the researcher as she was also handling Bukidnon-Magahat learners in the school where she is teaching. She also encountered challenges in having appropriate instruction and connections with the community since she was not a native of the community. It is on this premise that the researcher was interested to prompt the study on the influencing factors that affect indigenous learners’ academic performance. It is only in careful analysis of their shortcomings and even strengths when she can develop mechanisms which will help her indigenous students to become better versions of themselves, thus transcending them into a wide array of opportunities relevant to their over-all growth as a learner.

At present, no study in the local setting has yet explained the different factors that affect academic performance of Bukidnon-Magahat learners despite the mandate of DepEd order 32, s.2015 on the integration and contextualization of knowledge system, practices and learning system in educational context.

Research Design

The researcher utilized the descriptive-correlational method that uses statistics to measure the relationship between two or more items. It is descriptive in the sense that it describes indigenous learners’ perception on individual, instructional, and socio-cultural factors. On the other hand, it is correlational in nature because the perceived factors of indigenous learners were correlated to their academic performance.

Research Environment

The study was conducted to schools serving indigenous learners in the Schools Division of Bayawan City. The identified IP schools are Cabatuanan Elementary School of District 1, Basay, Negros Oriental, and Napo Elementary School of District 3, Bayawan City, Negros Oriental. Cabatuanan Elementary School is one of the farthest schools from Basay, Negros Oriental, approximately 20 kilometers from the municipality. The school’s location is in a highland/mountainous area of Barangay Cabatuanan, Basay, Negros Oriental. Because of this, there is insufficient water supply in the school. It has seven constructed building as an avenue for education and where learning takes place. Nowadays, it has electrical connection and some computer related facilities but no internet connection. In addition, there are a few mathematical tools and some science apparatus used to aid in the teaching-learning process.

Moreover, Cabatuanan Elementary School has a total enrollment of 174 indigenous learners for school year 2018-2019. There are 11 teaching staff including the school head, one teacher aide and two subject teachers from the school. Each grade level has one teacher one section ratio practicing a mono-grade type of classroom setting. Furthermore, the tribe has 1 mini native museum made up of bamboo materials and cogon where some of their indigenous materials were stored. The tribe has their Binuki language as their vernacular and still practicing their cultural beliefs and traditions in the community. On the other hand, Napo Elementary School is located in Sitio Napo of Barangay Tayawan approximately 30 kilometers from Bayawan City. Their primary source of income are sugarcane, and root crop farming. It is also situated in the mountainous area in the vicinity of ancestral domain claim in the locality of Bayawan City. The school is surrounded by huge tress, low water supply and has no electricity.

Furthermore, the school has a total enrollment rate of 120 in school year 2018-2019. It has two make shift classrooms and 5 functional classrooms. There are 7 regular teachers including the Head Teacher. Like the Bukidnons in Cabatuanan, Napo is also honoring their cultural practices in the community.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Grades 4-6 Bukidnon-Magahat learners, 79 respondents of Cabatuanan Elemenatry School and 60 from Napo Elementary School of Bayawan City Division.

Research Instruments

The major tool used in this study was the questionnaire. The questionnaire was a researcher-made tool. It was in English and was translated into Hiligaynon after it was referred to a native expert from Bukidnon-Magahat community. The self-made questionnaire is designed in such a way that identifies the factors the influence the academic performance of indigenous learners. The secondary data on indigenous learners' academic performance on the core subjects English, Science, and Mathematics of first and second quarter in school year 2018-2019 was gathered based on their grades in form 137. The first part of the questionnaire is composed of the indigenous learners' profile in terms age, gender, grade level and their academic performance on the core subjects: English, Science, and Mathematics during first and second quarters in school year 2018-2019.

The second part is comprised of the extent of perceived factors that might influence the academic performance of indigenous learners which include individual factors, instructional factors and socio-cultural factors. Prior to the preparation of the instrument, the researcher also read books, articles and other related materials relevant to the study.

To guarantee the reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher consulted a panel of experts and sought suggestions to the tribal council of elders on the content that was considered in the questionnaire. A dry run was conducted to 30 indigenous learners who were not part of the actual respondents and content was translated into community's mother tongue which is "Hiligaynon" for better understanding. To test the reliability of the tool, Cronbach's alpha test was used to find out if the items were valid. This test was regarded as the most suitable type for survey research where items were not scored right or wrong and where each item could have different answers. The dry run result indicated the following; individual factors 0.701 and some items were revised 0.702, instructional 0.805, and socio-cultural 0.702.

After the results, some indicators were suggested to be simplified like the individual factors on self-identity and academic achievement, socio-cultural especially items on parental support and indigenous communities. The researcher simplified the detected indicators and consulted her adviser and the statistician for the reliability of the content.

Research Procedure

After the design hearing, the researcher incorporated the corrections and suggestions of the panel members. A letter request was sent to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Bayawan City requesting permission to allow the researcher to conduct the study on the targeted schools in the elementary level in the Division of Bayawan City. Upon the approval of the request, a copy of the approved letter was given to the teacher-in-charge/head teacher/school principal of the participating school to allow the researcher to administer the questionnaire to the indigenous learners of Cabatuanan Elementary School and Napo Elementary School and so to have access on indigenous learners' official records.

On the day of the distribution of questionnaires, the researcher explained the purpose of the study and translated each indicator of the questionnaire to community's mother tongue which is "Hiligaynon" for better understanding. The researcher assured the respondents of the confidentiality of their responses. Right after, all the questionnaires were retrieved, the result was tabulated and tallied using MS Excel, was analyzed and was then interpreted.

Findings

Table 1. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Individual Factors in Terms of Identity

I am...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. preserving the cultural practices in our community (eg. Honoring traditions such as being hospitable and respectful to elders (aki/baye), following rituals to have good harvest, believing in babaylan as element healer and etc.).	4.27	Always	Very High
2. expressing myself freely as indigenous learner in individual and group discussion.	4.04	Often	High
3. honoring my cultural identity as bukidnon through performing tribal dances such as kinalasag, binanog and puntino during school activities like buwan ng wika or indigenous peoples day.	3.86	Often	High
4. wearing indigenous costumes like bahag/patadyong in the conduct of school activities or division celebrations.	3.15	Sometimes	Moderate
5. using indigenous language in communicating with my classmates and school mates.	2.65	Sometimes	Moderate
Composite	3.59	Often	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

It can be seen in Table 1 that the extent of perception of indigenous learners on individual factors in terms of their identity obtains an overall composite mean of 3.59 which denotes a verbal description of “high extent.” It is found out that indigenous learner’s perception in preserving the cultural practices in their community (eg. Honoring traditions such as being hospitable and respectful to elders, aki/baye), following rituals to have good harvest, believing in babaylan as element healer and etc. have a “Very High” extent as shown in the first indicator. This implies that indigenous learners believe that they have preserved their identity by preserving their beliefs and cultural practices.

On the other hand, the items which obtain the next highest ratings are indicators, they freely express themselves and honor their cultural dances. Moreover, they are on “moderate”

extent on wearing their tribal costumes during school celebrations and the use of their own language in communicating with their classmates and schoolmates.

This result is supported by the study of Purdie, Tripcony, Boulton-Lewis, Fanshawe, and Gunstone (2000). They found out that an indigenous child thinks about his or her cultural identity and exhibits pride in saying “I am black”, or “I am aboriginal,” “I honored my traditions and cultures as indigenous,” and this pride is derived mostly from family and indigenous community influences rather than from influences within the school or broader Australian community. However, it does not appear that most indigenous young people dwell on their identities; in some respects they do not perceive themselves to be different from non-Indigenous people—they listen to the same music, eat KFC, barrack for this football team or that, have future aspirations, and so on.

Table 2. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Individual Factors in Terms of Interest

Indicators	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. I listen attentively to the discussion of my teacher.	4.01	Often	High
2. I am prepared during test, quizzes, and examinations.	3.93	Often	High
3. I want to develop my skills and abilities in a culturally responsive classroom environment.	3.93	Often	High
4. I participate actively in the discussion , answer exercises and or clarify things I do not understand.	3.55	Often	High
5. I participate actively in school's extra-curricular activities.	3.46	Often	High
Composite	3.77	Often	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

Table 2 presents respondents' extent of perception in terms of interest. It garners an overall composite mean of 3.77 which denotes a verbal description rating of “high extent.” Data reveal that indigenous learners have “high” extent on their perception in terms of their interest

as indicated in all items. It means that respondents “often” listen attentively to the discussion of their teacher, prepare tediously to examinations, willingly develop their skills, and actively participate in extra-curricular activities. This implies that indigenous learners are actively engaged in classroom activities, thus their interest is on high extent.

This finding negates to the study of Reid (2008) wherein he found that most of the indigenous students in Australia have a very low interest in going to school due to the following reasons; (a) Parents and carers: parental-condoned absenteeism, parents failing to accept their legal responsibilities, and poor parental/carer attitudes towards schools. (b). Society: insufficiently valuing education and inadequate welfare support practices, especially in the early years of schooling. (c). Schools: poor teaching, inconsistent approach to absenteeism between, and within schools. (d). Students: bullying, peer pressure, ‘cool’ to skip school, lack of career aspirations, and low self-esteem.

Table 3. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Individual Factors in Terms of Study Habits

Indicators	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. I study harder to improve my performance when I get low grades.	4.01	Often	High
2. I study and prepare for quizzes and tests ahead.	3.85	Often	High
3. I prefer finishing my studies and my assignments first before playing or watching television shows.	3.65	Often	High
4. I spend my vacant time in doing assignments or studying my lessons.	3.56	Often	High
5. I have specific place of study at home which I keep clean and orderly.	3.36	Sometimes	Moderate
Composite	3.69	Often	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

The data in Table 3 show that the respondents often perceive that they have practiced the set of indicators in study habits with a composite mean of 3.69. As reflected, the respondents improve their performance whenever they get low scores and by giving themselves enough time to study. This implies that they have established their study habits.

Furthermore, they prefer to prioritize their school work than watching television at home. On the other hand, it can be gleaned that it is only sometimes when they have a study area at home.

Behrendt and McCausland (2008) advocate an evidence-based approach to increase the numbers of indigenous children attending and remaining at school. They found that the teachers' varied strategies help the indigenous learners to perform very well in the class. They further noticed that indigenous learners who are motivated by their teachers and parents had shown high extent on their study habits through active participation in class activities, submitted school projects on time, and willingness to learn is clearly depicted through their attendance and behavior inside the class.

Table 4. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Individual Factors in Terms of Academic Self-Concept

I am...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. determined enough to cope with school work.	3.96	Often	High
2. feeling good about my school work.	3.72	Often	High
3. proud of my performance in school.	3.68	Often	High
4. able to get the results I would like in school.	3.35	Sometimes	Moderate
5. capable of obtaining good grades.	3.15	Sometimes	Moderate
Composite	3.57	Often	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

The data in Table 4 reveal indigenous learners' extent of perception with regard to their academic self concept. It has an overall composite mean of 3.57 with a verbal description rating of "high extent." It is reflected that respondents highly perceive that they can cope with school work, feel good and proud with their school achievements. However, it is only sometimes when they get their their desired grades and results in school. This implies that learners still need to work on their desires to get good grades. Teachers and parents must challenge these learners to aim higher academic performance.

The result negates the study of Arens, Bodkin-Andrews, Gawaiian, Rhonda Yeung, and Alexander (2014) as they found that self-beliefs and school self-concepts of aboriginal students in Australia is at low level because they don't value much education and absenteeism is at high extent.

Table 5. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Individual Factors in Terms of Confidence in Academic Life

I am...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. having a good relationship with my teacher.	4.29	Always	Very High
2. very sure of myself before an exam.	3.48	Often	High
3. comfortable with extra work or activities.	3.43	Often	High
4. capable to compete with other learners in district and division activities.	3.18	Sometimes	Moderate
5. comfortable leading in academic group.	3.17	Sometimes	Moderate
Composite	3.51	Often	High

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

The data in Table 5 show that the overall composite mean of the respondents in terms of confidence in their academic life is 3.51 which is described as "high."

Data reveal that indigenous learners are having a very good relationship with their teachers as shown in the first indicator. This implies that respondents are comfortable with their teacher and are confident in communicating or responding to them. Furthermore, they have "high" level of self-confidence in examinations and with extra school works. However, sometimes they compete with other learners and lead in an academic group. This clearly means that teachers still need to develop the competitiveness and leadership skills of the learners.

The same finding was noted by Pidgeon (2008) wherein he showed that success for aboriginal peoples in postsecondary education also includes the "ability to maintain cultural integrity," "finding their gifts," and "responsibility of reciprocity," resulting to a high level of self-confidence in academic. Specifically, "maintaining cultural integrity," involves "having a sense of oneself and keeping hold of one's Indigenous understandings." An Aboriginal student's ability to "find their gifts" was defined as the capacity to do whatever a person envisions for himself or herself (Pidgeon, 2008a). The "responsibility of reciprocity" is the ability to give back to larger Indigenous communities (Pidgeon, 2008a). As such, for many aboriginal students' higher

education is recognized as an important tool for capacity building and assisting their communities to achieve their goals of self-determination and self-government (Pidgeon, 2008).

Table 6. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Instructional Factors in Terms of Teaching Strategies

My Teacher...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. translates popular stories using local languages that I would like to listen.	4.12	Often	High
2. uses local facts as examples for lessons such as plants, animals, persons, and practices found in the community.	4.05	Often	High
3. engages us to outdoor activities where we can see and manipulate real objects found in the community	3.82	Often	High
4. imposes group works/tasks in the class.	3.64	Often	High
5. uses technology aided instruction.	3.61	Often	High
Composite	3.85	Often	High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect
	4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Often	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

It is manifested in Table 6 that the respondents highly perceive the instructional factors in terms of teaching strategies amongst teachers with an overall composite mean of 3.85. Obviously, all indicators prove that teachers “often” translate stories using local languages, use local facts in lesson presentations, impose outdoor activities, generate group works and technology aided instructions in the classroom context. In general, teachers’ usage of varied teaching strategies is highly perceived by the indigenous learners. It can be inferred from this finding that incorporating different teaching strategies must be considered to cater the needs of the learners.

Likewise, Lewthwaite and Renaud (2009); Lewthwaite and McMillan (2010); Lewthwaite, Owen, Doiron, McMillan and Renaud (2013); and Lewthwaite et al., (2014) have identified pedagogical actions that influence effective teaching and learning and classrooms practices that have reduced the rupture between home culture and school for Indigenous students. The researchers along with community members participating in the research process refer to this practice as a ‘pedagogy of consequence’ (Lewthwaite et al., 2014). The researchers were able to identify through statistical methods the influences of these adjusted teacher behaviors on Indigenous students’ learning. Some of these behaviors include (1) explicit attention to supporting students in navigating the literacy and numeracy nuance of ‘schooling’; (2) adjusting

teacher communication patterns to ‘undertalk’ rather than ‘overtalk’; (3) communicating caring to students through actions such as high expectations, encouragement, challenge, and time spent with each student; (4) ensuring learning in classrooms that is not just centered on a teacher’s contribution; and (5) connecting learning to student’s lives, with special emphasis on those cultural/community elements that affirm local culture/community (2014).

Bishop and Berryman(2012) have identified a variety of practices that contribute to both positive learning environments and student success in learning practices. By doing so, they have developed an ‘Effective Teaching Profile’ for teachers of Maori students based on operationalizing interaction and pedagogical practices that students believe address and promote their educational achievement.

Both researches mentioned above are similar because they determine from the extent of perceptions of Indigenous students the teaching practices that contribute to their success as learners. These researchers then use students’ ‘voice in identifying teachers’ extent of instructional factors in terms of pedagogy and teaching strategy.

Table 7. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Instructional Factors in Terms of Instructional Materials/Devices

My Teacher...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. uses local resources as materials for instructional aides (eg. local plant dye for paints, parts of local plants to enhance posters and manipulatives, actual plants, soil, dry leaves, twigs or tree barks for art subjects and etc.).	4.15	Often	High
2. uses instructional materials in the class that we are familiar with.	3.99	Often	High
3. uses workbooks/textbook.	3.96	Often	High
4. encourages us to use indigenous materials in making our project/outputs.	3.65	Often	High
5. uses localized materials in presenting the lesson.	3.63	Often	High
Composite	3.88	Often	High
Legend:			
Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect	
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low	

Table 7 depicts that respondents show a “high extent” of perception on instructional factors specifically on instructional materials/devices with a composite mean of 3.88. The data reveal that indigenous learners has “high extent” of perception on teachers’ usage of local resources, textbooks, and indigenous materials for instructional aides as indicated in all items.

This implies that indigenous learners are familiar with the instructional materials used by their teacher and it can be inferred that these materials are found in their community.

Similar result was noted by Fien (2010), he concluded that the use of localized and indigenous teaching materials help lead students become more participative in class. This is due to opportunity to integrate their culture and tradition. This also aids them in attaining

awareness of the different indigenous groups. Students will be proud of their heritage and reverent to the heritage of others. This implies that there is a need to find ways on how indigenous knowledge may be integrated into education that will bring the benefits of helping society to sustain indigenous knowledge and to gain respect for local culture. Preparing and developing a localized indigenized instructional materials in teaching indigenous students will help them perform better in school.

Table 8. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Instructional Factors in Terms of School Program/Activities

I can...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. participate in school activities because I can sense belongingness with my classmates, school mates and my community.	4.05	Often	High
2. observe engaged community members and parents during school programs.	3.90	Often	High
3. learn indigenous knowledge, for our school allows culture bearers to impart knowledge in the classroom setting.	3.63	Often	High
collaborate with the community members for school activities.	3.58	Often	High
5. perform our traditional songs like idyuk and dinaklap during school activities such as buwan ng wika, indigenous peoples day and etc.	3.20	Sometimes	Moderate
Composite	3.67	Often	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect	
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low	

Table 8 indicates the respondents' extent of perception on instructional factors specifically in terms of school programs/activities. As noted, indigenous learners exhibit "high extent" on this area as reflected in the composite mean of 3.67. As reflected, they often participate in school activities, learn indigenous knowledge, collaborate with the community, and in observe community members during school programs. On the other hand, they display "moderate" extent of perception in performing their tribal songs during school activities. This implies that school initiated activities that involve community members where indigenous

learners can collaborate with in terms of school programs and educational instructions are often participate by indigenous learners.

One approach in engaging with indigenous students has been used to events or programs that have a focus on building cultural identity and pride in that identity, as well as a focus on promoting education, training and vocational pathways.

The Key Indicators 2009 report (SCRGSP 2009) presented the community festivals for Education Engagement program as an example of what works in increasing attendance for indigenous children at school in this way. The Community Festivals program (an Australian Government initiative) targets events that encourage students, particularly indigenous students, to attend school and lead healthy lifestyles. In 2008, five organizations were responsible for 15 festivals around Australia, including those held in remote locations. Students participate in concerts and cultural activities that endorse education, health, culture and potential vocational pathways (SCRGSP 2009).

Table 9. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Socio-Cultural Factors in Terms of Parental Support and Involvement

My Parents...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. support my needs in schools.	4.02	Often	High
2. educational attainment has influenced me in my studies.	3.99	Often	High
3. participation in school activities/meetings has guided me in my academic performance.	3.95	Often	High
4. are identified as culture bearers influencing me in terms of preserving our culture through teachings of indigenous terms/languages, sharing our tribal stories, beliefs and traditions.	3.76	Often	High
5. find time to follow up me in doing my assignments at home.	3.22	Sometimes	Moderate
Composite	3.79	Often	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect	
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low	

As reflected in Table 9, indigenous learners have “high extent” of perception on socio-cultural factors in terms of parental support and involvement with an overall composite mean of 3.79. As shown on the four items, respondents have “high” level of perception on their parents’ support, participation, educational attainment influences on their progress and in preserving their culture. However, parents’ follow-up activities on their children at home appeared to be “moderate.” This suggests that parents have high level of influence in terms of their

participation and support on their children's academic achievements in school. It can be inferred that the higher involvement they have the better performance they will attain.

This finding negates to the study of Reid (2008) wherein he found that parent and carers of indigenous children condoned absenteeism, parents failing to accept their legal responsibilities, and poor parental/carer attitudes towards schools.

Furthermore, Frecker (2001) found that aboriginal students agree that schools are making an effort to encourage aboriginal parental involvement in the education process but that parental involvement at school is still limited. However, many school staff believed that aboriginal families do not value or support the education process at home, while aboriginal parents expressed their value of education and reported involvement to varying degrees, in their children's learning at home.

Additionally, she found that both school staff and parents value parental involvement at school. However, school staff value parental involvement that engages parents as agents of the school, while parents value involvement that allows them to monitor the safety and performance of their children at school (2010).

Table 10. Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Socio-Cultural Factors in Terms of Indigenous Communities

Community's...	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
1. elders perform tribal dances like kinalasag, binanog, and puntino in the conduct of school-based Indigenous Peoples' Day.	3.94	Often	High
2. elders and other stakeholders participate in community engagement activities like making of indigenous dictionaries, grammar, and stories.	3.81	Often	High
3. council of elders coordinate with teachers on Indigenous Peoples Education (IPed) implementation in the school through conferences and meetings.	3.56	Often	High
4. barangay officials cooperate during school activities like brigada eskwela.	3.55	Often	High
5. culture-bearers find time to share their knowledge on Bukidnons's Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP's) such as pakusad, pa-pa-an, planting rituals, indigenous polite expressions and tribal beliefs in the classroom setting.	3.16	Sometimes	Moderate
Composite	3.60	Often	High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Effect	
4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Often	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low	

Table 10 presents the extent of perception of indigenous learners on socio-cultural factors in terms of indigenous communities. It can be noted that the composite mean is 3.60 denoting a “high extent.” It reveals that respondents have “high” level of perception on community members participation like elders who are performing tribal dances, making

indigenous dictionaries and stories, involving them on meetings and conferences, and engaging barangay officials during school activities. However, culture bearers are on “moderate” level in terms of imparting their cultural beliefs and practices in the classroom setting. It can be implied from the findings that indigenous communities have high level of participation and involvement in schools activities in the hope of revitalizing and preserving their cultural practices through knowledge transmission to indigenous learners.

Aboriginal studies programs in schools have always had a major focus on the formation of positive relationships between the school and the aboriginal community, relationships that are based on mutual respect and understanding. This conforms to Wray’s study (2006), in his study on the Aboriginal Studies course and the importance of Aboriginal community members actively engaged in Aboriginal Studies classes. It was revealed in his study that for both aboriginal students and community, there was an opportunity to reinforce the learning that had taken place in the classroom with those Elders or other Aboriginal community members who they came in contact with. It became, for the majority of the students, “better learning” as it was “real” and “hands-on.” Both groups could see this as of high importance in terms of authentic cultural experiences. In contrast, Aboriginal students felt more strongly about the connections made with the community, seeing it as a means of strengthening their cultural ties with the Aboriginal people in their community. With many aboriginal students experiencing ‘a loss of culture’ due most often to the breakdown in aboriginal families and communities and more importantly the loss of the teaching process passed on by Aboriginal Elders.

There was also an indication that for aboriginal students, their identity was valued in turn raising high self-esteem and confidence, providing high cultural affirmation and pride, this was linked to the teacher’s efforts in establishing community networks and their role in the successful implementation of aboriginal studies (Board of Studies NSW, 2008). This study was supported by Wa-Mbaleka and Safary (2013) found that there was a strong relationship between the school and the indigenous community. When parents take them to these schools, they must promise to feed their children three meals a day, and must provide clean clothes to them. Communities are also expected to lend their hand in some basic construction activities of the school. Teachers provide some workshops on better farming techniques. Additionally, they educate the Katutubo to reject any business deals (such as sale of land or goods) that take advantage of them. At times, when Katutubo communities run out of food, teachers sometimes feed them. Lastly, Board of Studies NSW (2008) supported that, to enhance the learning experience of all students and promote reconciliation through better understanding, schools and the local Aboriginal community need to develop strong relationships that are maintained through a collaborative approach. To ensure that the relationship is meaningful, schools need to listen to the views of Aboriginal people and learn from the knowledges that are shared, showing respect through proper community protocols.

Table 11. Summary Table of the Extent of Perception of the Indigenous Learners

Factors	μ_w	Verbal Description	Extent of Perception
Individual Factors			
Identity	3.59	Often	High
Interest	3.77	Often	High
Study Habits	3.69	Often	High
Academic Self-Concept	3.57	Often	High
Confidence in Academic Life	3.51	Often	High
Instructional Factors			
Teaching Strategies	3.85	Often	High
Instructional Materials/Devices	3.88	Often	High
School Program/Activities	3.67	Often	High
Socio-Cultural Factors			
Parental Support and Involvement	3.79	Often	High
Indigenous Communities	3.60	Often	High
Legend:			
Scale		Verbal Description	Extent of Effect
4.21 – 5.00		Always	Very High
3.41 – 4.20		Often	High
2.61 – 3.40		Sometimes	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60		Seldom	Low
1.00 – 1.80		Never	Very Low

Table 11 presents the summary of indigenous learner's perception on individual factors, instructional factors and socio-cultural factors. It reveals that all major indicators contain "high" level of extent as perceived by the indigenous learners. The individual factors and study habits rank high with a weighted mean of 3.69, while confidence in academic life rank least with a weighted mean of 3.51.

On instructional factors, instructional materials/devices rank first as it has a mean of 3.88, while school programs/activities rank least with a mean of 3.67. Moreover, in socio-cultural factors, parental support and involvement ranked higher than indigenous communities. Thus, data reveal that indigenous learners showed a "High extent" on their individual, instructional, and socio-cultural perceived factors.

This is supported by Purdie, Tripcony, Boulton-Lewis, Fanshawe, and Gunstone, (2000). They noted that one of the most important contributors to the development of a positive sense of self as an indigenous person within the context of the school is the extent to which individual teachers exhibit an acceptance and valuing of Indigenous people and their culture. Aboriginal

students in Queensland university perceived high extent on the individual factor such as positive self-concept, self identity, and interest in schooling. Furthermore, they noted that Aboriginal students wanted to come to school because it had good teachers, and a good program. This implies that they are interested to go to school and increase their academic self-concepts and confidence. Additionally, Fien (2010) noted that the use of localized and indigenous teaching materials help lead students become more participative in class.

Table 12. Academic Performance of Indigenous Learners in Core Subjects

Core Subjects	1 st Quarter		2 nd Quarter	
	μ	Verbal Description	μ	Verbal Description
English	79.00	Fairly Satisfactory	80.09	Satisfactory
Science	79.43	Fairly Satisfactory	80.24	Satisfactory
Mathematics	79.86	Satisfactory	80.29	Satisfactory
Mean	79.43	Fairly Satisfactory	80.21	Satisfactory

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description
	90% - 100%	Outstanding
	85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
	80% - 85%	Satisfactory
	75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	Below 75%	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 12 shows the data on indigenous learners' academic performance on the core subjects, namely: English, science, and mathematics. It reveals that the academic grade of the respondents on first quarter contain a "fairly satisfactory" rate with an overall mean of 79.43. The core subjects, English and science are rated "fairly satisfactory" in the first quarter with the mean score of 79.00 and 79.43 respectively, while, mathematics is rated as "satisfactory" as it obtains a mean score of 79.86. On the other hand, respondents' academic performance manifests an increasing grade in second quarter in all the core subjects as it is clearly rated as "Satisfactory" with the mean of 80.2. Meanwhile, of the core subjects, mathematics obtain the highest rating as shown in the table from first to second quarter.

This implies that learners have developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and with little guidance from the teacher and/ or with some assistance from peers, and can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks (The explanation is based on DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012).

The result of the study is similar to the investigation conducted by Andaya (2016) where freshman students have satisfactory performance in their 4 core subjects such as Filipino, English, Math, and Science.

Table 13. Relationship between the Perception of the Indigenous Learners on the Different Factors and Their Academic Performance

Factors	Computed r_s	Degree of Relationship
Individual Factors		
Identity	0.025	Very Weak
Interest	0.463	Moderate
Study Habits	0.534	Strong
Academic Self-Concept	0.542	Strong
Confidence in Academic Life	0.581	Strong
Instructional Factors		
Teaching Strategies	0.005	Very Weak
Instructional Materials/Devices	0.116	Weak
School Program/Activities	0.008	Very Weak
Socio-Cultural Factors		
Parental Support and Involvement	0.342	Moderate
Indigenous Communities	0.097	Very Weak

Legend:

Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	\pm strong relationship
Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	\pm moderate relationship
Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	\pm weak relationship
Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	\pm very weak relationship

Table 13 shows the data in identifying the relationship between the different factors that may influence indigenous learners' academic performance. In terms of individual factors, their interest ($r_s = 0.463$) is moderately related with their academic performance. Meanwhile, their study habits ($r_s = 0.534$), academic self-concept ($r_s = 0.542$) and confidence in academic life ($r_s = 0.581$) are strongly related to their academic performance. This further implies that the higher the perception of the learners on these variables, the better is their academic performance. Andaya (2016) found a different result, her study revealed that there is a low correlation between academic performance of Indigenous students and their individual factors such as interest and study habits.

On the other hand, learners' perception on their identity is not related to their academic performance. This means that whether they perceive high or low in their identity, their academic performance is more or less the same. The result is similar to Bagley, (2010) where high self identity is not significantly related to their academic performance.

With regards to the three instructional factors, data reveal that the relationship with their academic performance is either weak or very weak. This connotes that whether they perceive high or low on these factors, their academic performance is more or less the same. Instructional factors show low correlation with academic performance. This result tries to indicate that instructional factors like medium of instruction, teachers' motivation, teacher's competence and the like has a little effect on their academic performance. Balili (2013) pointed out that student learns or perhaps more accurately prefers to learn in different ways. The simple facts that many teachers teach different groups in the same manner, but students' success varies. One concept that may shed light on difference on students' success.

On the other hand, data gathered by Andaya (2016) negated this result, she found that instructional factors affect academic performance to a large extent, she further revealed that teachers have a major effect on student's achievement. She highlighted the role of teacher's quality and effectiveness. The findings revealed that for the students to accomplish learning, teachers should provide meaningful and authentic learning activities to enable students to construct their knowledge of the subject domain. Thus, instructional factors is significantly related to the academic performance of indigenous learners. Also, the study of Barry (2005) and Maximo (2015) revealed that teacher is the essential feature in the delivery system of teaching learning process. Teachers should apply best methods for producing learning and students' success.

As to socio-cultural factors, parental involvement is moderately related to their academic performance. This means that the higher the parental involvement, the higher also is the academic performance of the learners. This is also supported by Faircloth, and Tippeconnic (2010). They found that parental involvement in school is moderately related to the academic performance of the Indigenous learners. Parents who often visited school show that they are concerned with the academic status of their children.

However, the perception of the learners on the involvement of the indigenous community is not related to their academic performance. This signifies that that whether they perceive high or low on this factor, their academic performance is more or less the same. This implies that indigenous community does not directly influence the academic standing of the learners but teachers do (Maximo, 2015).

Conclusions

Below are the conclusions generated based on the findings of the study:

1. Individual, instructional, and socio-cultural factors revealed to have a “high” influence on indigenous learners’ academic performance.
2. The academic performance of the respondents on the core subjects such as
3. English, Science, and Mathematics is “Fairly Satisfactory” on the first quarter and satisfactory level during the second quarter.
4. The data revealed that there is a strong relationship between the individual factors like study habits, academic self-concept, and confidence in academic life on their academic performance. Meanwhile, they are on moderate relationship in their interest. A very weak relationship on instructional factors, and moderate extent on parental support.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

1. The parents are encouraged to constantly follow up the academic performance of their children by attending regular PTA meeting and making a follow up on their follow up on their children’ progress at home.
2. Teachers may hone the talent and skills of Bukidnon-Magahat learners by including them in any school and division activities so that their academic self-concept, study habits, and confidence will improve.
3. During school activities, teachers may encourage their indigenous learners to present their cultural songs during Buwan ng Wika or Indigenous Peoples’ day. This will increase the self confidence of the indigenous learners. Furthermore, teachers integrate Bukidnon-Magahat’s Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices(IKSP’s) in every subject area through contextualization and indigenization of lesson plans, learning resources and teaching strategies to improve indigenous learners academic performance.
4. Indigenous elders are encouraged to continue to share their practices and tradition in the school setting through scheduled class sessions, meetings and conferences.

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APPENDIX
Questionnaire
(English Translation)

Factors Influencing Academic Performance of Indigenous Learners

This questionnaire aims to identify the “Factors that Influence the Academic Performance of Grade 4-6 Indigenous Learners”. Please fill up the questionnaire with the needed information and be objective with your responses. Rest assured that your responses will be held confidential. Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Instruction: Fill in the necessary information on the space provided for each item.

Part I. Personal Profile:

Name: _____ Grade Level: _____

Sex: _____ Age: _____

Grade of the following core subjects in SY:2018-2019: (advisers will provide this part)

	English	Science	Mathematics
First Quarter :	_____	_____	_____
Second Quarter :	_____	_____	_____

Part II. Extent of the perceived factors that may have influence academic performance of indigenous learners

Instruction: On a scale from one to five, check (√) ONE answer that would best describe the extent of each factor (as expressed in each of the statement) had influenced you or still influencing you. Each response option on the scale is rated as in the following:

Scale	Verbal Description	Equivalent	Explanation
5	Always	Very High	The activity/feeling is done/felt 81-100% of the time
4	Often	High	The activity/feeling is done/felt 61-80% of the time
3	Sometimes	Moderate	The activity/feeling is done/felt 41-60% of the time
2	Seldom	Low	The activity/feeling is done/felt 21-40% of the time
1	Never	Very Low	The activity/feeling is done/felt 1-20% of the time

Individual Factors	SCALE INTERPRETATION				
	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
A. Identity					
I am...					
1. expressing myself freely as indigenous learner in individual and group discussion.					
2. wearing indigenous costumes like bahag/patadyong in the conduct of school activities or division celebrations.					
3. using indigenous language in communicating with my classmates and school mates.					
4. honoring my cultural identity as bukidnon through performing tribal dances such as kinalasag, binanog and puntino during school activities like buwan ng wika or indigenous peoples day.					
5. preserving the cultural practices in our community (eg. Honoring traditions such as being hospitable and respectful to elders (aki/baye), following rituals to have good harvest, believing in babaylan as element healer and etc.).					
B. Interest	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
1. I listen attentively to the discussion of my teacher.					
2. I participate actively in the discussion , answer exercises and or clarify things I do not understand.					
3. I am prepared during test, quizzes, and examinations.					
4. I want to develop my skills and abilities in a culturally responsive classroom environment.					
5. I participate actively in school's extra curricular activities.					

C. Study Habits	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
1. I spend my vacant time in doing assignments or studying my lessons.					
2. I study and prepare for quizzes and tests ahead.					
3. I study harder to improve my performance when I get low grades.					
4. I prefer finishing my studies and my assignments first before playing or watching television shows.					
5. I have specific place of study at home which I keep clean and orderly.					
D. Academic Self-Concept I am...	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
1. capable of obtaining good grades.					
2. determined enough to cope with school work.					
3. proud of my performance in school.					
4. feeling good about my school work.					
5. able to get the results I would like in school.					
E. Confidence in Academic Life I am...	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
1. comfortable with extra work or activities.					
2. very sure of myself before an exam.					
3. having a good relationship with my teacher.					
4. comfortable leading in academic group.					
5. capable to compete with other learners in district and division activities.					

Instructional Factors	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
A. Teaching Strategies My Teacher...					
1. translates popular stories using local languages that I would like to listen.					
2. engages us to outdoor activities where we can see and manipulate real objects found in the community					
3. uses local facts as examples for lessons such as plants, animals, persons, and practices found in the community.					
4. imposes group works/tasks in the class.					
5. uses technology aided instruction.					
B. Instructional Materials/Devices My Teacher...	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
1. uses local resources as materials for instructional aides (eg. local plant dye for paints, parts of local plants to enhance posters and manipulatives, actual plants, soil, dry leaves, twigs or tree barks for art subjects and etc.).					
2. uses localized materials in presenting the lesson.					
3. uses instructional materials in the class that we are familiar with.					
4. encourages us to use indigenous materials in making our project/outputs.					
5. uses workbooks/textbook.					

C. C. School Program/Activities I can...	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
1. participate in school activities because I can sense belongingness with my classmates, school mates and my community.					
2. perform our traditional songs like idyuk and dinaklap during school activities such as buwan ng wika, indigenous peoples day and etc.					
3. learn indigenous knowledge, for our school allows culture bearers to impart knowledge in the classroom setting.					
4. collaborate with the community members for school activities.					
5. observe engaged community members and parents during school programs.					
Socio-cultural Factors	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
A. Parental Support and Involvement My Parents...					
1. are identified as culture bearers influencing me in terms of preserving our culture through teachings of indigenous terms/languages, sharing our tribal stories, beliefs and traditions.					
2. educational attainment has influenced me in my studies.					
3. participation in school activities/meetings has guided me in my academic performance.					
4. find time to follow up me in doing my assignments at home.					
5. support my needs in schools					

B. Indigenous Communities Community's...	Always (5)	Often (4)	Sometimes (3)	Seldom (2)	Never (1)
1. elders and other stakeholders participate in community engagement activities like making of indigenous dictionaries, grammar, and stories.					
2. elders perform tribal dances like kinalasag, binanog, and puntino in the conduct of school-based Indigenous Peoples' Day.					
3. culture-bearers find time to share their knowledge on Bukidnons's Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSP's) such as pakusad, pa-pa-an, planting rituals, indigenous polite expressions and tribal beliefs in the classroom setting.					
4. council of elders coordinate with teachers on Indigenous Peoples Education (IPed) implementation in the school through conferences and meetings.					
5. barangay officials cooperate during school activities like brigada eskwela.					